
IMPORTANCE OF YOUTUBE VIDEOS IN THE LANGUAGE TEACHING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the importance of using social platforms that meet the requirements of the current technology age in teaching English, namely You Tube. The YouTube website is regarded as one online material that can be integrated into traditional English lessons. It is also considered a source of online material that can play a vital role in the teaching and learning field. By using videos on the YouTube platform, it becomes possible to organize the lesson process in an interesting way and to convey a lot of information to the learner in a short time. This study reviews some of the work that has been done so far.

Keywords: *You Tube website, Online materials, Technology, eLearning, EFL.*

We know that in today's technologically advanced age, ways to receive all kinds of information faster and easier are developing. And automatically, educational content on online platforms like You Tube is also expanding. Ultimately, eLearning through videos is an attractive way to learn a new foreign language. E-Learning adds a dynamic element to learning, improves knowledge production, makes complex processes easier to reproduce, and helps to try to multiply topics. Careful supervision, they are fun to watch and readable. This is the reason why video sharing websites like YouTube are so popular to enhance and improve the knowledge of the course. This article attempts to reveal the importance of YouTube videos and general websites in the preparation and creation of English language teaching video materials.

Before using all kinds of online materials, it is necessary to pay attention to how many students or residents of the country have the opportunity to use the Internet. According to the article provided by Uzreportnews.uz: "How much of the population of Uzbekistan uses the Internet?" It is said that: In the report issued by the Canadian company Hootsuite, there are 18.6 million Internet users in Uzbekistan. Compared to

2020, this indicator increased by 263,000 (+1.4%) [1] This shows that more than 50% of the 34 million inhabitants of Uzbekistan have access to and use of the Internet.

In addition, the attention to language learning can be seen in the state's policy. In accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to bring the activities of popularization of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level" dated May 19, 2021 No. PQ-5117, as well as foreign languages in order to effectively implement organizational measures for the popularization of learning, the Cabinet of Ministers decides and accordingly forms the legal basis for organizing the educational process on the basis of recognized foreign and international standards; the possibility of conducting the educational process remotely (online) through automated programs and video courses was considered.

A teacher is needed to support the teaching of English as a foreign language consider and encourage appropriate teaching techniques and tools for students. In teaching a foreign language, using the World Wide Web (WWW) as a resource. The development of mastery of the English language was an important thing to achieve an important result (Medukali, 2015). Video has an advantage for learners because it reflects body language and something contextual and gives students a “short attention span” (Yasin et al., 2018). People like watching video as entertainment in daily life, but video can be as media teaching and learning English as a foreign language. When people watch videos, especially English videos, subconsciously they learn to listen to their ears in every way and language processing. Students who watch the video can understand its meaning video chat. The most visited online video platform is YouTube. Part of YouTube online media that includes a variety of videos created by people who become its content creator According to (Kabooha & Elyas, 2015), YouTube is a multidimensional resource includes video in all areas of knowledge for easy access. Using in ESL classes YouTube allows students to use their native language in a natural context (Nurholida, 2016). It may be the best option to fulfill your need to learn English as a foreign language. Teachers can use YouTube videos as a follow-up method the student's listening and speaking skills, as it can be enjoyed only with the help of sight and hearing (Watkins & Wilkins, 2011). Styati (2016) states that using YouTube increases students' interest in learning. English is easier. In this study, the researcher found that YouTube is real Material for teaching the four skills in English language acquisition. YouTube is a permissive video platform its users have important freedoms to express and share information. In addition,

YouTube a free media that allows its users, including students and teachers around world to easily view and upload their videos (Muhammad et al. 2014).

Usually, teachers look at YouTube as a base of video materials for developing speaking and listening skills, but given the variety of content on YouTube, there are also educational materials aimed at developing reading and writing skills. Examples of these are the following YouTube pages:

- Reading English page that has more than 5 thousand followers and 150 plus videos about correctly pronouncing words and reading fluently;
- Doses of English page that involves stories in English with audio and text formats;
- English Languages academy with overall 3.48 million followers and more than 2 thousand videos to develop reading comprehension;
- Learn English through stories page that has stories in English in all levels.

Through the You Tube pages mentioned above, teachers can independently choose or create activities. And of course, activities should match the level and interests and age of the class. In this regard, we can use the Note-taking and summarizing method proposed by (Watkins, J., & Wilkins, M. 2011a): Although this activity could be used for high beginner and pre-intermediate level students, it works best for students at the intermediate level or above. The note-taking and summarizing activity requires students to use YouTube to listen to lectures on various topics, take notes on the main points and important details, verbally check and expand their notes with a partner, listen again to further expand their notes, and then write summaries from their notes. They can then look at a transcript of the clip and compare their summaries with those of their classmates and teachers. If the students' summaries differ considerably from the teacher's, then the teacher can point out why he or she chose the information included in the model summary.

To sum up, You Tube is an easily accessible and free base of video materials that can be utilized both in teaching and learning English language. Another advantage of you tube platform is that you don't need any lengthy registrations to use it, you just need a good internet speed. You tube contains video materials that can cover all four skills in teaching English and the most convenient and optimal video demonstrations for the use of today's youth.

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